

WORK SATISFACTION AMONG INDIAN RAILWAY EMPLOYEES WITH REFERENCE TO SCR.

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ABSTRACT

In this report, the researcher sought to investigate the job satisfaction of Indian railway personnel. The primary purpose is to recommend more developments in Indian Railway (IR) as well as to collect employee feedback in South Central Railway (SCR). Fortunately, in this study, employees are willing to offer ideas to IR; employees are at comfortable in SCR, therefore absenteeism is low; and employees are always accessible to help IR. The study's findings are all positive.

Keywords: Work satisfaction and career enjoyment, IR, SCR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Workplace happiness is an inward experience. It can only be inferred based on how behavior is expressed. It's interesting that it is invisible and immaterial. We also have ideas that explain job/work satisfaction. The most significant ideas in this area, including the Steady State Theory, Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory, The Facet Model, and Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory, have been explored below. These many theories of work satisfaction complement one another and aid managers in understanding the various facets of job happiness so that they may comprehend the various components and difficulties they need to take into consideration to raise the level of satisfaction among their subordinates. By dissecting a job into its constituent parts, or job facets, and examining how pleased employees are with each aspect, the aspect Model of Job Satisfaction focuses largely on work environment characteristics. The total of a worker's contentment with each aspect of the job is used to calculate overall job satisfaction. Employees might consider a variety of characteristics of their work when evaluating their levels of job satisfaction, as shown in table 1.1. The facet model is beneficial because it makes managers and researchers realize how various aspects of employees' lives are impacted by their professions. However, managers should be mindful that, for any given job, they may unintentionally leave out a crucial aspect that has a significant impact on an employee's job satisfaction when using this model to assess the impact of the work environment on job satisfaction. For many employees, a crucial aspect of their jobs is whether or not the employer is family-friendly. Family-friendly organizational policies and perks are becoming more and more essential to employees as a result of the growing diversity of the workforce and the rise in the proportion of women, couples juggling

two careers, and single parents who must balance their duties at work and at home. Additionally, managers who utilize the aspect model of work satisfaction must take into account a number of additional factors, one of which is the possibility that some job features may be more crucial for a particular employee than others. For instance, family-friendly policies are frequently valued by employees who have children, but they are unquestionably less significant for employees who are single and expect to stay that way. Nevertheless, working from home may have benefits for working parents and those with long commutes, but it may not be a good fit for younger employees who value social engagement with coworkers. In addition to the aforementioned factors, income and job stability may be crucial components of work satisfaction for a single woman with high extrinsic values. To sum.

Objective: To study the level of work satisfaction among the IR Employees.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The level of a person's job satisfaction reflects how much they like their work. For some people, work is enjoyable and an important aspect of life. Others simply go to work because they have no choice but to. In the fields of organizational behavior and industrial-organizational psychology, this job attitude has been the focus of substantial investigation. This section will give a full analysis of the significance, root causes, and effects of this crucial employee attitude. The nature of job satisfaction will be covered first, with an emphasis on its historical roots, significance, and dimensions. The discussion of various important assessment methods will follow. The third section will include an explanation of the causes or predictors of work satisfaction. Lastly, the results of work satisfaction will be looked at.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Actions Taken For the Job

Employees are the foundation of every company. Employee work makes company objectives a reality. Employees that have the necessary abilities for the job are a tremendous value to the company. Any organization's ability to succeed depends on the dedication, initiative, and efforts of its employees. Over time, deliberate efforts have been made to align employee competence with the new challenges posed by technological advancements and changes in the business environment.

Table 1

S.No.	Variables	Frequency	Percent
1.	Do you shield IR's assets from dangers?	276	100
2.	Do you provide IR any useful recommendations?	136	49.3
3.	Do you promote IR in a positive way?	276	100.0
4.	Do you believe that a job well done contributes to reducing absenteeism?	218	79.0
5.	Do you believe that a job well done contributes to reducing staff turnover?	208	75.4

6.	Whether or whether your job happiness contributes to IR's performance improvement.	229	83.0
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According to Table 1, every employee in the entire sample stated that they safeguard IR's assets in dangerous situations. Even the sample employees who work in the commercial and transport departments all agreed on the same ideas. According to the study above, workers safeguard IR's assets when there are dangers. The bulk of the sample's respondents 49.3 percent of them are interested in offering ideas to IR. It is clear that most employees are not eager to offer advice concerning internal relations. All responders from the whole sample agreed that they only discuss IR in a good light. Even the sample employees who work in the commercial and transport departments all agreed on the same ideas. According to the study, workers had favorable things to say about IR. The majority of respondents in the entire sample, or 79.0 percent of them, expressed positive thoughts. It is clear from the data above that employee work satisfaction contributes to reducing absenteeism. The following is shown by examining the views of the staff in the commercial and transportation departments. Seventy-five percent of the employees, or 75.4 percent, of them, voiced good thoughts. It is clear that employee work satisfaction contributes to reducing staff turnover. The bulk of the employees, or 83.0 percent of them, voiced their sentiments favorably. It may be stated that employee work satisfaction aids in enhancing IR performance.

Table 2

S.No.	Job Satisfaction – Organizational Factors	Mean	Rank
1	Job security is provided by Indian Railways (IR).	4.35	6
2	Good earnings and salaries are paid by IR.	4.37	4
3	Paying salary and wages promptly (Promptly)	4.39	3
4	Bonuses and other perks are occasionally paid by IR (perks).	4.04	14
5	As excellent as those paid by other transportation businesses, IR's wages and salaries (Payments)	4.10	12
6	The working environment in IR is favorable (Working environment)	3.01	15
7	Safety is of the highest concern to IR.	4.45	2
8	In IR, the work is tough (Challenges).	4.36	5
9	The work burden in IR is within reasonable ranges.	2.34	16
10	Opportunities are provided for IR employees to put their talents and abilities to use.	4.17	10
11	In IR, there is autonomy (Autonomy)	1.93	17
12	Promotions are given based on qualifications rather than bias (Performance).	4.22	9
13	The techniques used to advance personnel are fair and transparent (Transparent)	4.16	11
14	In IR, promotions are given out when appropriate.	4.10	12

15	The reasonable and equitable policies of IR (Policies)	4.25	7
16	Employees who exhibit exceptional performance at work are recognized and given prizes by IR (Recognition).	4.46	1
17	To the pleasure of the workforce, IR offers welfare amenities.	4.25	7

Table 2 displays the mean value of employees' perceptions of their job satisfaction in relation to organizational traits. The highest mean value (4.45) in the table is for safety, which is followed by timely payment of wages (4.39), earnings (4.37), obstacles (4.36), protection (4.35), regulations (4.25), social assistance (4.25), achievement (4.22), skills (4.17), accountability (4.16), promotions (4.10), payments (4.10), gains (4.04), conditions of employment (3.01), work load (2.34), and independence (1.93). The highest mean value (4.46) is for recognition. From the chart, it can be inferred that employees think Indian Railways compensates individuals who do very well at work.

4. CONCLUSION

According to the study, the researcher was encouraged to contact IR with staff ideas that should be taken into account as soon as possible for the department's progress and employee happiness. Employees are eager to provide ideas because they regard the IR as a part of their family. The railways' performance, facilities, and other characteristics are typically positive, and we all have positive things to say about IR. Employees are less inclined to skip out on their tasks because of the favorable work environment's attitude toward peers, bosses, and organizational laws.

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